

Thematic Classification Hydronimes of Kashkadary and Andijan Regions

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Annotation: Modern processes of globalization lead to a sharp change in the vocabulary of national languages, both quantitatively and qualitatively. The whole world knows that languages that have abandoned their values, history and their origins and fallen under the influence of hegemonic languages are gradually disappearing.

It is quite obvious that when representatives of any nation fight for the fate of their native language and fight for its development, the prestige of such languages increases not only in our country, but also in the international arena.

Uzbek language is one of such languages. The collection, recording and linguistic classification of names associated with the history, national traditions and values of our people is one of our most important tasks in preserving its future.

Onomastic names are considered lexical units that have this status. Among them, terms related to water occupy an important place in the Uzbek language, as a clear expression of millenniums.

For example, springs, streams, rivers, lakes, ponds, wells and similar hydronyms in the Kashkadarya and Andijan regions, located at the two ends of our Republic, give us valuable information about the worldview, customs and centuries-old history of our people. Their lexical-semantic and structural features are of particular importance in revealing the unique features of the Uzbek language.

Accordingly, in this article, using the example of hydronyms of the Kashkadarya and Andijan regions, the lexical-semantic groups of water names, which are one of the richest and oldest layers of vocabulary of the Uzbek language, are analyzed.

Keywords: language, linguistics, onomastics, onomastic sphere, scale, toponym, antropogidronim, topogidronim, etnogidronim, fitogidronim, zoogidronim.

Text.

From time immemorial, the most important task of man was to live in living nature. The struggle for survival forced a person to always think, think, discuss his opinion with others, and most importantly, find the purpose of life at a certain time. Banks, streams, rivers and lakes have been convenient places to live in all eras. Water has always been the source of life for humans.

Therefore, since ancient times, people have treated water extremely carefully. It is everyone's duty to conserve and use water sparingly and to respect it. Maintaining clean water is one of the laws of society. Based on this, people learned to call each source of water by a separate name. They named springs, streams, rivers, wells, etc. based on the benefits they brought to people, and not because of their color or location.

For example, the river flowing through the Pakhtaabad and Izboskan districts of the Andijan region was called Tentaksoy (Crazy stream), because during spring floods it overflowed its banks, disrupted its course and caused great damage to people. A source of water with similar characteristics in Kashkadarya is called Jinnidarya (Psycho stream). A very similar, unique nomination – these words reflect the entire nature of the river.

In fact, since ancient times, people have given different names to each feature of the earth to distinguish their places from each other. V. A. Nikonov, one of the experts in this field, said that over time, cities and states may decline, languages and even peoples may disappear forever, but the names given to them will never be lost. [Nikonov, 1965, 15].

In this regard, toponyms in Uzbekistan occupy a special place. The unique grace, beauty and richness of the Uzbek language are clearly expressed in the names of cities and villages, rivers, springs, mountains, hills, in a word, toponyms – toponyms. This can be seen in the example of old and popular toponyms of the Kashkadarya and Andijan regions.

It is known that the linguistic unit used to distinguish toponyms from each other is called a toponym. The toponym comes from the Greek words *topos* – place and *onoma* – name, a branch of lexicology that studies toponyms, meaning a set of toponyms in a certain territory [Hojiyev, 2002, 110].

Geographical names are a broad concept. Includes about 100 geographical objects, such as “proper names of natural geographical and artificial (man-made) objects located on the earth’s surface: oikonym, oronym, speleonym, horonym, urbanonym, drimonim, necronym, from the point of view of linguistics, it includes onomastic volumes and volumes” [Begmatov, Uluqov, 2006, 76-77].

One of them are names associated with water – hydronyms. Hydronym is formed from the Greek words *hydor* – water, *onoma* – noun and includes the names of running and standing water and reservoirs [Hojiyev, 2002, 30].

In this article we tried to identify general and specific aspects of the hydronyms of the Kashkadarya and Andijan regions.

It is known that toponyms contain more ancient phonetic, lexical and morphological elements unique to each language. The natural and geographical conditions of a place, the ethnic composition of the population, professions and occupations of people, mineral resources, the names of the people who founded this place, historical figures and events related to their activities are the main linguistic sources for the creation of toponyms [Uluqov, 2008, 35].

This situation is especially strong in names associated with water. Such names can be found in Uzbekistan and in both regions. N. Ulukov, who defended his doctoral dissertation on hydronyms in valley regions, said that there are 6,500 hydronomic names in the Fergana Valley. The work identifies 36 types of them [Uluqov, 2008, 4-19].

Based on the materials we collected, we tried to divide them into microgroups.

1. Names of sources.

For Kashkadarya region: *Abdalbuloq, Ayirg‘a, Arpabuloq, Beshbuloq, Bodaki, Bo‘talabuloq, Gulbog‘, Gulbuloq, Gumbaz, Devonbuloq, Yonabu, Yong‘oq, Jangalbuloq, Jiyda, Jiydali, Junivoybuloq, Zirkbuloq, Kamar, Ko‘kcha, Qamashibuloq, Qashmuyar, Qizilbuloq, Qizilqo‘ton, Qoqbuloq, Qoraqara, Qo‘ng‘izbuloq, Qo‘riq, Qo‘tirso‘lak, Lo‘libosti, Obichashma, Oqbuloq, Olabuloq, Polabuloq, Sabziq, Sassiqlihashma, Tovulchak, Tomchi, Toshbuloq, Xarkalla, Xo‘jane‘mati, So‘rbuloq, So‘rcha, Cho‘yansoy* and others.

In Andijan region: *Shirmonbuloq, Oybuloq, Oqbuloq, Sovuqbuloq, Fozilmon ota bulog‘i, Abduhakimbuloq, Shirag‘anbuloq, Uchbuloq* and others.

2. Thread names.

For Kashkadarya region: *Ajirchasoy, Arabbandi, Gov, Darxon, Denov, Jaztepa, Jar, Janbo'z, Ko'lob, Qamashi, Qorasuv, Qoratepa, Qoracha, Qumariq, Loyqa, Mo'minobod, Oqariq, Po'lati, Savbog', Sariq, Xabar, Xonobod, Xo'jaariq, Yangikent* and others.

In Andijan region: *Damariq, Yov, Yozyovon, Jo'ga, Qaqir, Qatortol, Miyon, Naynavo, Katta ariq, Do'stariq, Nishab, To'rko'lkanda, Uyshshinariq, Xakan, Xo'ja, Eshon, Yangiariq, Xonariq* and others.

About ditches in Andijan Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur: "Nine streams of water enter. Surprisingly, it doesn't come out anywhere," he writes [Bobur, 1960, 58]. Babur used the word *tarnov* instead of *arik*.

Andijan residents have preserved the names of these 9 streams: *Khakanarik, Burkhansheikh, Joybazar, Khotanarik, Bogrokhan stream, Okravot, Tokmok, Bobotavakkal, Dalvarzin*.

TARNOV [persian: *water flows, passing pipe*] A device made of wood or tin in the form of a pipe or gutter, which is installed along the edges of the roof to drain rain and snow water [Isaqov, 2006, 65].

3. Story names.

For Kashkadarya region: *Abdi, Ajirchasoy, Almatsoy, Arabbandi, Baqati, Beshqo'ton, Beshsoy, Bulquloq, Bulutxona, Varanko'loiy, Voxinsoy, Gandagerim, Gandasoy, G'elon, Govxona, Govxonasoy, Guldara, Gumushlik, Gurati, Gurlunlak, Davronsoy, Dandonchakan, Darasoy, Dashsoy, Dug'ob, Do'konxona, YElsoy, Javaqli, Jar, Jarsoy, Jarshashir, Zarangzorsoy, Zoqchisoy, Ingichka, Ingichkasoy, Sichqonsoy, Yo'natsoy, Ichkalibuloq, Ichkilik, Kavraysoy, Kallasoy, Kindik, Kindiktepa, Kon, Ko'kashsoy, Ko'kdaryo, Kunko'rmas, Kuyukdaryo, Qaynarbuloq, Qayrag'ochsoy, Qizilangur, Qizilgaza, Qizilko'l, Qizilsoy, Qishloqsuv, Qovluq, Qoplondara, Qora archa, Qora dahana, Qoranko'l, Qorako'loiy, Qorasuv, Qorachashma, Qorong'iliksoy, Qo'ybor, Qo'rnonak, Qo'rg'onaksoy, Qurko'l, Qursoy, Quruqlisoy, Quruqsoy, Qutchi, Qushliq, Qushtivasoy, Quyuqchinor, Langar, Mamarli, Navdarz, Navchaqar, Obakihonaqo, Obishxondaryo, Oyoqchidaryo, Oqquldiqsoy, Oqota, Oqravot, Oqsoy, Oqsuv, Oqtosh, Olayluq, Omonchiqsoy, Otxona, Oftobro'ya, Oxirgiqishloqsoy, Oxirgisoy, Polvonsoy, Rahimsoy, Salimsoliq, Sangpassoy, Sanginak, Sarituz, Sarito'qay, Sarich, Sarobi, Soyjilg'ako'l, Suvjar, Suvlisoy, Suvtushar, Takalik, Tarag'aysoy, Temirsandiq, Temiro'g'li, Tirna, Terakli, Toldi, Tomchisoy, Toshbuloq, Toshqal'a, To'laqo'loiy, To'lasoy, To'tko'l, To'rtqo'yliq, Uvildilik, Uyshinsoy, Ulug'dala, Fayzullo, Xo'jaqo'rg'on, Xo'jaorolsoy, Chaqcha, Chappasuv, Chashmai kanda, Chashmai obizamzam, Chilhazor, Chimboy, Cho'yanlisoy, Sharda, Shardaryo, Shirindaryo, Sho'rdaryo, Sho'rsoy, Egrisuv, Yaroqsoy* and others.

In Andijan region: *Andijonsoy, Shahrixonsoy, Moylisoy, O'rmonsoy, Yangi Naynavo, Tentaksoy* and others.

4. River names.

For Kashkadarya region: *G'ulondaryo, G'uzordaryo, Jinnidaryo, Katta O'radaryo, Kichik O'radaryo, Qashqadaryo, Qizildaryo, Qorasuv, Qumdaryo, Oqdaryo, Oqsuv, Tanhozdaryo, Yakkabog'daryo* and others.

In Andijan region: *Norin, Qoradaryo, Arabonsoy, Sirdaryo, Xolmurod, Qolzandaryo, Norin* and others.

5. Channel names.

For Kashkadarya region: *Beshariq, Bo'ston, Darxon, Jeynov, Zarbuloq, Imomyoqub, Koson, Lagandi, Makrat, Mirishkor, Mudun, Navqot, Obinavot, Paxtaobod, Pistaxon, Po'lati, Rudaksoy, Sandal, Ushoqtepa, Fazli, Xitoy, Chil, Qamrad, Qavchin, Qoributan, Qumdaryo, Halqabod* and others.

In Andijan region: *Katta Farg'ona kanali, Katta Andijon kanali, Janubiy Farg'ona kanali, Shimoliy Farg'ona kanali, Qurama, Chinobod, Do'stlik, Yangi Ko'ratma, Savay, Tuyamo'yin, Karkidon, Paxtaobod, Ulug'nor* and others.

6. Names of collectors.

For Kashkadarya region: *Badaxshon, Dasht, Duyul, Jonboz, Juyruk, Zax, Loyqa, Uzunquduq, Tinibek, Xonobod, Shamolquduq, Sho 'rsoy, Sho 'rcha, Yangidaryo, Qalli, Qorabayir, Qorabog 'soy* and others.

In Andijan region: *Zambarko 'l, Sariqsuv, Sherqo 'rg 'on, Mazgilsoy, Jo 'ga, Abduamat, Sariqjo 'ga, Chyegara* and others.

7. Lake names.

For Kashkadarya region: *Qorabuloq, Tortar, Tuyako 'l, Halimko 'l, Sho 'rko 'l* and others.

In Andijan region: *Ko 'l, Oltinko 'l, To 'rko 'l, To 'dako 'l* and others.

8. Reservoir names.

For Kashkadarya region: *Berdi, Bozorko 'l, Karim, Kyelin, Langar, Latta, No 'g 'ayli, Pachkamar, Uvana, Xo 'ja, Chilgumbaz, Chimqo 'rg 'on, Shamshiqoq, Sho 'rabsoy, Yangiqo 'rg 'on, Qalqama, Qamashi, Qizilsuv, Hamro, Hisorak* and others.

In Andijan region: *Andijon, Kampirobod, Otchopar, Asakaadir* and others.

9. Names of glaciers not found in other places in the Kashkadarya region: *O 'rtachilhazor, Chapchilhazor, Chilhazor, Yakka; Suvtushar; Jar, Sangak, Qirlisoy; quduq nomlari: Taqirquduq, Cho 'lyotoq, Alaqum, Po 'lat bobo, Shirinquduq, Mo 'minyotoq, Sho 'rko 'lyotoq, Qurbonboy, Beshquduq, Obbaquduq, Sutxona, Yutar, Berdiquduq, Avazcho 'l, Hachcha, Qo 'shjarli, Daraxtli, Kapali* and others.

From the practice of studying toponyms, it is clear that when studying the geographical names of a certain territory, it is recommended to pay attention to their various parameters in order to achieve significant results in the study and classification of toponyms [Superanskaya, 1970,18].

Results and discussions. The results obtained show that hydronymic names in both regions form a landscape unique in scale and linguistic features. In particular, lexical-semantic groups of hydronyms help us clarify the subtle features of the nomination of a spring, stream, river, lake, well and similar names. They can be grouped as follows.

- 1. Anthropohydronyms:** *Almatsoy, Davronsoy, Rahimsoy, Salimsolik, Fayzullo* (river names); *Imomyokub* (channel name); *Tinibek* (collector's name); *Berdi, Karim* (names of reservoirs); *Polat Baba, Mominotak, Gurbanboy, Berdiguduk, Avazchol* (names of wells) and so on. These are hydronyms that arose on the basis of a person's relationship to a place (object) [Axunov, 1997, 29].
- 2. Ethnohydronyms:** *Lolibosti, Khojanemati* (spring names); *Arabbandi, Uishinsoy, Khojakurgan, Khojaorolsoy* (river names); *Darkhan, China, Kavchin* (channel names); *Nogaili, Khoja* (names of reservoirs) and others.
- Ethnotoponyms are toponyms formed from the names of a people, nationality, clan and their participation. Among them, ethnohydronyms occupy an important place. [Karimov, Bo 'riyev, 2006, 43].
- 4. Phytohydronyms:** *Arpabulok, Gulbog, Gulbulok, Walnut, Dzhangalbulok, Dzhiida, Dzhiidali, Zirkbulok* (generic names); *Guldara, Zarangzorsoy, Kavraysoy, Saritokai, Terakli, Toldi, Kayragochsoy, Karaarcha, Kuyukchinor* (river names); *Boston, Pistachon* (names of canals) and others.
- It is noteworthy that the poetic thinking of the people was manifested in phytohydronyms. Our opinion can be confirmed by the hydronyms *Pistachon* and *Kuyukchinar*.
- 6. Topohydronyms:** *Kamashibulok, Kamashi, Yangikent* (names of streams); *Varankolsoy, Vukhinsoy, Kyshlaksuv* (names of rivers); *Guzordarya, Yakkabogdarya* (river names); *Navkot, Polati* (channel names); *Badakhshan* (collector's name) and others.
- 7. Zoohydronyms:** *Kongizbulok, Gov, Govkhona, Govkhonasoy, Sichhansoy, Koplondara, Koibor, Otkhona, Takalik, Karabair, Tuyakol*.

8. **Names associated with color:** *Kokcha, Karabulok, Kyzylbulok, Kyzylkoton, Karakara, Akbulok, Olabulok* (spring names); *Karasuv, Karatepa, Karacha, Saryk* (names of streams); *Kokashsoy, Kokdarye, Kizilangur, Kyzylgaza, Kyzylkol, Kyzylsoy, Kara Archa, Kara Dakhana, Korankol, Karakolsoy, Karasuv, Karachashma, Akkuldiksoy, Akota, Okravot, Aksoy, Aksuv, Aktash* (river names); *Kyzildarya, Karasuv, Akdarye, Aksuv* (river names); *Karabayr, Karabogsoy* (names of the collector); *Karabulok, Kyzylsuv* (name of a reservoir) and others.
9. If you pay attention, with the help of a black hydraulic element a spring, stream, creek, collector, reservoir, etc. is created. This indicates the activity of this lexical unit in the creation of hydronyms.
10. **Names associated with the number:** *Beshbulok* (name of a stream); *Beshkoton, Beshsoy, Tortkol, Tortkoilik* (river names); *Besharik* (channel name); *Beshkuduk* (name of the well) and others.
11. **Names associated with quality:** *Botalabulok, Kakbulok, Kotirsolak, Polabulok, Sassikchashma, Shorbulok, Shorcha* (spring names); *Mutny* (stream name); *Kyzylgaza, Korongiliksoy, Kuruglisoy, Kuruksoy, Kuyukchinor, Shirindaryo, Shordarya, Shorsoy, Egrisuv* (river names); *Dzhinnidarya, Kashkadarya* (river names); *Uzunkuduk, Shamolkuduk, Shorsoy, Shorcha* (collector names); *Halimkol, Shorkol* (names of lakes); *Latta, Shorabsoy* (names of reservoirs) and others.
12. **Weather-related names:** *Bodaki* (name of a stream); *Elsoy* (name of the river); *Windmill* (collector's name) and others.
13. **Hydronyms formed using the lexeme Chashma:** *Obichashma, Sassikchashma* (names of streams); *Karachashma, Chashmai kanda, Chashmai obizamzam* (names of rivers), etc. The word *Chashma* comes from the Persian word *chashma* – *bulak*, source, and means “a source of water coming out of the earth, and its water” [O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati, 2008, 495].

In the Andijan region, due to the fact that the Persian-speaking population is not densely located along the banks of the water, hydronyms formed by springs are almost never found. There are many representatives of such a population in the Kashkadarya region, and it is quite natural to come across such hydronyms as indicated above.

Conclusions. Based on the above, we can come to the following conclusion: hydronyms denoting the names of running and standing waters: springs, ditches, canals, lakes, etc., in the territory of both regions form a rich onomastic layer of the Uzbek language. They clearly express the worldview, customs and way of life of the peoples living here. Lexico-semantic groups of hydronyms confirmed the variety of ways to name water sources. A significant part of this layer consists of hydronyms based on the names of a specific person, clan, tribe, people.

The nominations also highlight interesting facts related to trees in the area where water sources are located, wild animals nesting near the water, color, number and size. The study of such names is of particular value when studying the moments of thinking of our people.

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